

Impact of Procrastination on Self-esteem of College and University Students of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 16, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: April 17, 2023</p> <p>Keywords : Procrastination, Self-esteem, Students, Active Or Passive Procrastination</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7834334</p>	<p><i>The present study investigated procrastination and self-esteem among College and University students of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The sample of the study consists of (N=272) out of which 133 were males and 136 were females and they were taken from different colleges and universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa through convenience sampling technique. It was assumed that male students will score higher on Lay Procrastination Scale as compared to female students and that active procrastinator students have high self-esteem as compared to passive procrastinator students. Lay Procrastination Scale (Lay, CH. 1986) and Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (Rosenberg, M. 1965), were administered. Significant association between procrastination and self-esteem, among students was measured by using the T-test. The results of the study supported that procrastination did have a significant relationship with self-esteem.</i></p>

Introduction

Procrastination has been practiced by humans for centuries. The problem is so old that it was addressed by the ancient Greek philosophers such as Aristotle and Socrates who coined the term *Akrasia* to characterize this type of behavior. It is the state of behaving in contrast to your best decision. It is when you do one thing even though you know there is something else you can do. You might claim that *Akrasia*, roughly translated, is a lack of self-control or procrastination (Clear, 2012).

We all know the saying "Never put what you can do today away for tomorrow". We all have postponed and delayed things that tell us "I'm going to finish it later for sure". It's not always easy to control this kind of behavior, while we are conscious that we waste a lot by procrastinating. Procrastinating is a well-known psychological phenomenon, and two fields have been broadly studied; neurotic indecision and academic procrastination (Milgram et al., 1988). The former, which is the subject of this research, refers to the pause and delay in completing tasks and preparing for exams (Ely & Hampton, 1973; Haycock et al., 1998).

The act of delaying or postponing a task or collection of tasks is known as procrastination. Therefore, if you refer to it as *Akrasia* or procrastination or anything else, it is the power that prevents you from accomplishing your goals (Clear, 2012).

Procrastination is something most individuals have at least a small amount of familiarity with. No problem how well-organized and dedicated you are, it's likely that you've been wasting time on idle pursuits (updating your Facebook status, shopping online watching TV, etc.) when you should have spent the time on work or school-related projects (Solomon & Rothblum, 1984). Procrastination can have a significant effect on your grades, your career, and as well as on your life, whether you are putting off completing a project for college, ignoring household chores, or skipping homework assignments. At some time or another, we all procrastinate, and according to the researchers, the problem may be mainly acute among students. Approximately 25 to 75% of college students delay academic work (Ferrari et al., 2006; Tibbett et al., 2015).

Procrastination was practiced by 80 to 95 percent of college students on a regular basis founded by a study, mostly when it came to completing coursework and assignments (Steel, 2007). A study showed that one of the main causes of why Ph.D. candidates struggle to complete their dissertations was procrastination. Academic procrastination is caused by a number of major cognitive distortions.

- Exaggerate how inspired in the future they will be
- They exaggerate the amount of time they have left to finish assignments.
- Assume wrongly that working on a project needs them to be in the right frame of mind
- Underestimating how long it would take those activities to complete

Steel (2007) found that students who were procrastinators stated fewer sicknesses and lower levels of stress than non-procrastinators. Procrastinators had significantly higher levels of stress and sickness by the end of the semester.

Procrastination can not only have a bad effect on well-being, but it can also harm your social relationships. You place a burden on the people around you by putting things away. The people who rely on you such as your fellow students, friends, and family, will become resentful if you usually send in projects late until the last minute (Sirois, 2015). It is not necessary for procrastination to dominate your life. You will be able to prepare yourself to resolve procrastination with the right knowledge and find your inner concentration and inspiration.

Knaus (2000) said that not all delays relate to adversarial effects. As an example, delays can be beneficial, arising from time spent preparing and collecting important preparatory details. Many people believe that they can still finish on time even though they start working at the last minute and that they are inclined to work harder and quicker or produce more innovative ideas under time constraints (Ferrari *et al.*, 2006; Tibbett *et al.*, 2015). This school of thought on procrastination indicates that there are many types of procrastinators and that procrastination may often produce positive outcomes (Choi, 2005).

Procrastinators can be classified into two types: active and passive procrastinators. Passive procrastinators are procrastinators in conventional wisdom. Passive procrastinators do not want to procrastinate in the first place, they may not plan to procrastinate, however, they are unable to make decisions quickly and therefore act quickly on them, as a result of their inability to do so, and they sometimes end up postponing tasks. On the other hand, active procrastinators are able to move on to their decisions quickly. However, they purposely drop their acts and concentrate their emphasis on other important tasks at hand (Choi & Chu, 2005).

Consequently, the cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects of passive procrastinators vary from active procrastinators. Passive procrastinators feel stressed and become negative in outlook as a deadline approaches, particularly about their capability to produce suitable outcomes (Ferrari *et al.*, 1992).

In order to produce different behavioral patterns, various cognitive processes and affective responses interact. At the last minute, active procrastinators are diligent and able to finish tasks. Passive procrastinators, on the other hand, are much more likely to give up and struggle to complete chores. It is indicated that active procrastination is a multilayered phenomenon that involves *affective* (fondness for time constraints), *behavioral* (task completion by the deadline), and *cognitive* (decision to procrastinate) as well as the physical outcome and satisfaction with them. Due to these basic distinctions (affective, behavioral, and cognitive), active and passive procrastinators were expected to have different psychological features and to attain distinct results (Choi & Chu, 2005).

Researchers point in the direction in which procrastination increases the anxiety of students and decreases their self-esteem (Yorukoglu, 2004). Bukra and Yuen (1983a) did the most convincing research in this respect. Low self-esteem according to their model of procrastination, is an essential component of procrastination. An individual who procrastinates begins to feel helpless and powerless, his faith suffers, and the future appears obscure. Self-esteem is often influenced by procrastination, regarded as having a positive or negative approach to life (Ferrari *et al.*, 1995).

Self-esteem is a subjective assessment of one's own worth based on a collection of thoughts and feelings. It is, to put it another way, the expression used to describe people's emotions and thoughts about their entire self-worth. People with high self-esteem are known to have a wide range of coping mechanisms when faced with problems and are more likely to tackle emotional obstacles, whereas people with low self-esteem are known to have a limited range of coping strategies and are more likely to face emotional challenges (Mahesh, 2019).

According to Di Fabio (2006), decisional procrastination and self-esteem have an inverse relationship.

Steel (2010) discovered that relationships exist between various indicators of procrastination and desire for sensation, self-esteem, and the fear of failure. Milgram, Marshevsky, and Sadeh (1995) found out that students more often consider explanations for academic procrastination that were less detrimental to their self-perception (e.g., time management issues) than those who were more menacing. It is highlighted that in the event of a possible loss, in terms of self-esteem, procrastination acts as a protective mechanism (Burka & Yuen, 2008, Covington, 2007; Duru & Balkis, 2014; Ferrari *et al.*, 1995). According to Burka and Yuen (2008b), procrastinators assume that their achievements reflect their self-worth. Therefore, in the event of a possible loss, they conclude that they are not only ineffective as a person but also for doing the current task. In this case, to preserve their self-worth, they refrain from doing that job. Likewise, Thompson (1999) also suggested that by procrastinating, people who are uncertain in relation to their ability to accomplish a task effectively attempt to maintain their self-esteem. Plentiful research has highlighted the link between procrastination and self-esteem (Balkis & Duru, 2012; Ferrari & Diaz-Morales, 2007; Park & Sperling, 2012; Pychyl *et al.*, 2002). In short, excessive procrastination is likely to be associated with low self-esteem.

It will examine how academic achievement and self-esteem interact, which are thought to be linked to procrastination and well-being. Former studies have shown that procrastination predicts self-esteem and self-esteem expects emotional adaptation and comfort (Bajaj *et al.*, 2016; Duru & Balkis, 2014; Ferrari, 2000; Lin, 2015). In other words, self-esteem decreases as the level of procrastination rises, and this has a negative impact on well-being. A significant and growing public health concern is mental health among university students.

Self-esteem plays a significant role in our lives because our success is influenced by the way we view ourselves, and this in turn affects how we see ourselves. Although low self-esteem can prevent us from thriving, high self-esteem can help us to prosper (Sameer et al., 2019). Shahnawaz, (2016) conducted a study on “procrastination among students: the role of gender, perfectionism, and self-esteem”. Data was gathered from 100 young college students (50 men and 50 females) enrolled in Delhi's colleges and institutions. The general procrastination scale (Lay, 1986) and Frost multidimensional perfectionism scale (Frost et al., 1990) were offered to them. Gender was found to be a major predictor of procrastination in the study, with males scoring higher on procrastination and perfectionism than females.

A study on “procrastination and self-esteem-A gender-based study” explored by Gohil (2014). A sample of 101 participants (51 females, 50 males) was selected from the University of Jammu. Lay's general procrastination scale and Rosenberg self-esteem scales were used as instruments. There was no substantial variance in procrastination between male and female participants but was a significant difference in self-esteem across gender, so female participants had higher self-esteem than male participants.

“Relationship between self-efficacy, self-esteem, and procrastination in undergraduate psychology students” was investigated by Hajloo (2014). A sample of 140 undergraduate Psychology students (83 females and 49 males) were selected. Instruments used for data collection were the self-efficacy scale, Rosenberg self-esteem scale, and the student version of the general procrastination scale were used. The results revealed higher levels of procrastination were linked to lower self-efficacy and self-esteem.

Duru and Balkis (2017b) conducted a study on “procrastination, self-esteem, academic performance, and well-being: A moderated mediation model”. A sample of 348 undergraduate students were selected in which 73% were consisted of female students. The Students age ranged were 19-26. Turkish version of Tuckman's (TPS-TV) 14-item self-report test of procrastination scale and Rosenberg 10-items self-report measure were used to assess the level of self-esteem and procrastination among Turkish sample. Procrastination and self-esteem were found to be significant predictors of satisfaction, with a high level of procrastination having a direct effect on self-esteem.

Babu; *et al.* (2019) find out “relationship between academic procrastination and self-esteem among dental students in Bengaluru City”. For this purpose a sample of 255 (127 males & 127 females) undergraduate dental students were selected in Bengaluru colleges. Tuckman's 14-items measure was used to classify academic procrastination and Rosenberg self-esteem scale for both positive and negative feelings about one self. It was discovered students with high self-esteem procrastinate less, while those with low self-esteem procrastinate more.

A study on “relationship between procrastination and self-esteem among males and females university students” was investigated by Naveed and Ishtiaq (2015). A sample of 200 (100 males & 100 females) students between the aged ranged of 17-24 were selected. Lay procrastination measure and Rosenberg self-esteem scale were used. Male students are more inclined to postpone than female students, according to the research, and as procrastination increases, so does self-esteem.

Tamini; *et al.* (2013) investigated a study on “academic procrastination and its relationship with self-esteem and life satisfaction”. A sample comprises of 206 students (101 females and 105 males) age ranged from 20 or below 35 were selected using simple random method. The Lay procrastination scale (1986), Heatherton and Polivy (1991) self-esteem scale and Huebner (1994) life satisfaction scales were used. Self-esteem was found to be negatively correlated with procrastination, and there was a significant negative correlation between procrastination and satisfaction with life.

Objectives

- To find out gender differences among procrastinated students.
- To assess the extent of self-esteem and procrastination among college and university students.
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Hypotheses

- Male students will score high on procrastination scale as compared to female students.
- Active procrastinators students have high self-esteem as compared to passive procrastinator students.

Methodology

Sample

A total sample of 272 students (N=272) of which 136 were females and 133 were males between the age range of 18 and 25 years, were selected through convenience sampling technique from different colleges and universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (University of Peshawar, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Women University Peshawar, Agricultural University Peshawar, University Of Swat, Post-Graduate Jahanzeb College Swat and Govt. Post Graduate Girls Degree College Saidu Sharif Swat).

Instruments

Procrastination scale (1986)

Lay (1986) created the Academic Procrastination Scale to measure students' procrastination. It has 20 elements, each of which can be scored from extremely uncharacteristic (1) to extremely characteristic (5). "I often find myself doing activities that I had planned to do days before," for example, is one of the things that participants are asked to answer to. Higher scores reflect passive procrastinators while lower scores indicates active procrastinators. Lay reported 0.89 reliability of the scale (Ashman & Hull, 2016).

Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (1965)

Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale. It was a 10-item scale that measured global self-worth using both negative and positive approach to evaluate the self (e.g., "I feel that I have a number of good qualities"; "At times I think I am no good at all"; "I take a positive attitude toward myself"). The scale was uni-dimensional (Rosenberg, 1965). All items were answered on a 5-point Likert scale format ranging from strongly agree = 5 to strongly disagree = 1. Items 2, 5, 6, 8, and 9 were reverse scored. Sum of scores for all ten items was

treated as total score. The score ranged from 10 to 50. Higher scores indicated higher self-esteem. Reliability and validity of the scale has been well established in documented studies (e.g., Baumeister, Campbell, Krueger, & Vohs, 2003; Ciarrochi, Heaven, & Fiona, 2007). The alpha reliability for the present study was .81.

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The Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale is a 10-item test that uses a negative and optimistic approach to self-evaluation to measure one's overall self-worth (e.g., "I believe I have a lot of good qualities," "At times I believe I am not good at all"). It was a one-dimensional scale (Rosenberg, 1965). All questions were answered on a 5-point Likert scale, with 4 indicating strong agreement and 1 indicating strong disagreement. In the opposite order, items 2, 5, 6, 8, and 9 were scored. The total score was determined by adding the results of all ten items. The score ranged from ten to fifty. Higher scores showed a higher level of self-esteem, while lower scores showed a lower level of self-

esteem. The scale's reliability and validity have been well-known in researches (e.g., Baumeister et al., Ciarrochi et al., 2007). Test-retest reliability for the RSES is 0.85 (Blascovich et al., 1993).

Procedure

In the present study, sample were selected from different colleges and universities. Permission was taken from the Head of the institute. Rapport was developed with students and they were briefed about the aim of the study after that Consent form was given to each student in order to know their willingness to participate in the study. The Lay Procrastination Scale and Rosenberg Self Esteem Scale were directed to measure their level of procrastination and self-esteem. Instructions were given to them about filling out the questionnaire and were informed about the confidentiality of their data.

Results

Table 1

Mean, Standard deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, and Alpha Coefficient of Procrastination Scale, and Rotter Locus of Control Scale.

Scales	N0.of items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Conbranch' Alpha
PS	20	64.9	8.77	.162	.147	0.7
RSES	10	28.7	3.63	2.68	21.7	0.8

Table 1 shows the α -reliability coefficient and descriptive statistics for the PS and RSES.

Table 2

Means, standard deviation, and *t*-values of the scores of male and female on lay procrastination scale ($n=272$)

Group	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>P</i>	95%CI		<i>ULCohen's d</i>
					<i>LL</i>	<i>UL</i>	
Males ($n=133$)	59.0809	7.48832	-2.875	.004	-4.73510	-	0.35
Females ($n=136$)	56.2707	8.50056	-2.879	.004	-4.73219	-88822	

Results of table 2 shows considerable difference between male and female procrastinators on lay procrastination scale. The results suggested that male students procrastinate more than female students, so it's supported the hypothesis.

Table 3

Means, standard deviation and *t*-values of active and passive procrastinator students on self-esteem scale.

(95%CI)

Procrastination	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>LL</i>	<i>UL</i>	<i>Cohen's d</i>
Active	181	28.0884	4.48738	-2.432	.016	-2.57675	-2.26672	0.32
Passive	75	26.6667	4.15684	-2.356	.019	-2.60995	-2.23351	

Results in table 3 shows significant difference between active and passive procrastination and that active procrastinators students have high self-esteem as compared to passive procrastinators, and thus supported our hypothesis.

Discussion

Procrastination is the failure to create objectives or prioritize goals, which can make it difficult for students to complete work or fulfill deadlines on time (Hoover, 2005). Employees are frequently seen procrastinating and completing projects just before submission deadlines in a variety of settings, including the workplace (Beheshtifar, Hoseinifar and Moghadam, 2011). Students are prone to procrastination, and many researchers have looked into how they approach meeting deadlines (Chun Chu, and Choi, 2004).

It was hypothesized that "Male students will score higher on procrastination than female pupils" (H1). Procrastination is a problem for students. Studies proved that procrastination is common among male students (Prohaska et al. 2000). Male students have a habit to postpone tasks until the last minute. For instance, they postpone classes, group projects, examinations, academic papers or theses. This type of student may only

be able to accomplish tasks in order to pass the course. Procrastination can be explained by a variety of factors, including fear of failure, incompetence, and low self-intelligence. Procrastination is caused by a lack of motivation, which is influenced by behavioral and emotional processes associated with task avoidance situations (Rothblum, Solomon & Murakami, 1986). Many researches have revealed that procrastination is more widespread in male students than female pupils. Result of the present study (table 2) revealed a substantial difference in scores between male and female procrastinators. Male pupils are more likely to postpone than female students. The result supported the hypothesis of the study. Research conducted by Arif; et al. (2014) "Academic Procrastination among Males and Females University and College Students" A total of 200 students (100 college and 100 university students) from various colleges and universities in Islamabad were included in the sample, ranging in age from 16 to 27. Male students procrastinate more than female students, according to the findings.

Considering the second hypothesis "Active procrastinator students have high self-esteem as compared to passive procrastinators" (H2). Self-esteem can be affected both directly and indirectly by procrastination. A person with low self-esteem and a negative attitude toward himself has a significant impact on his academic performance, such as absenteeism, poor performance, bad grades, and mental health, because of these feelings, self-esteem plummets and self-doubt rises (Yorukoglu, 2004). In order to account for the potential that not all procrastination actions are harmful, we conceptualized two sorts of procrastinators (Chu & Choi, 2005). Active procrastination is linked to a sense of control over one's time, emotional stability, self-reported performance, and overall happiness. Passive procrastination, on the other hand, a self-destructive process in which failure to complete tasks and meet deadlines is followed by self-doubt, anxiety, and distress (Choi & Moran, 2009). Active procrastinators have a self-destructive time management approach that permits them to work under pressure while yet achieving deadlines. According to Beilock and Carr (2004) self-reported scores on active procrastination are favorably connected with autonomy, psychological well-being, personal growth, environmental mastery, life purpose and positive relationships, while passive procrastination is adversely associated. Result of the present study (table 3) shows significant difference between active and passive procrastinators and also its association with self-esteem. The results revealed active procrastinators' students have high self-esteem as compared to passive procrastinators. Same results were given by Zhou, M. (2018) "Effects of personality on procrastination: does it vary by gender". The goal of the research was to get a better understanding of both active and passive procrastination, as well as their correlations with personality in both men and women. Cuncolker, S. & D'Silva, C. (2018) examine "Relationship between procrastination, self-esteem, self-efficacy and motivation among college students". A total of 60 students from various colleges were chosen. The researchers wanted to see if there was any correlation between self-esteem, procrastination, motivation, and self-efficacy in pupils. Tuckman procrastination scale, the general self-efficacy, Rosenberg self-esteem scale, and academic motivational scales were used. The study's findings indicate that procrastination and the other characteristics analyzed have a substantial relationship (self-esteem, self-efficacy and motivation). The same findings were supported by Rafique, R., & Saleem, M. (2012) "Procrastination and self-esteem among university students". The primary purpose of the study was to determine whether there was a link between procrastination and students' self-esteem. A sample of 80 students (39 males and 41 females) were chosen. The findings revealed a strong negative relationship between procrastination and self-esteem "Predictors of academic procrastination in College students" was investigated by Farran, B. (2004). For this purpose a sample of 186 students were selected. The study's goal was to see how different self-perceptions, or attitudes about oneself, influenced academic procrastination. Self-report measures were completed by participants in which academic self-concept (Academic Self-Concept Scale) academic procrastination (Procrastination Assessment Scale-Students), academic self-efficacy (Academic Self-Efficacy Scale), depression (Beck Depression Inventory-Second Edition) general self-esteem (Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale), and anxiety (Beck Anxiety Inventory). It was also expected that academic procrastination would be associated with depression and anxiety in a significant and positive way. The study's findings backed up these theories. Higher levels of academic procrastination related with higher levels of sadness and anxiety, as well as they have higher unfavorable judgments of their general self-worth, self-worth as a student, and sense of efficacy in academic tasks.

Conclusion

Student procrastination is a typical manifestation. Even though they are aware that procrastinating is harmful to their academic performance, they find it difficult to stop. Fear of criticism is one of the reasons why some students procrastinate. Ferrari (1992) uncovered a new, very distinct reason for procrastination to protect pupils' self-esteem and identity beliefs. He discovered that learners began working on an assignment because they were excited about the prospect of working against a deadline. The goal of the existing study was to examine the relationship between procrastination and self-esteem. It is concluded that male students as compared to female students procrastinate more. The current study discovered a substantial positive link between self-esteem and procrastination.

Limitations

- 1- The participants were the initial constraint. It's difficult to get an honest answer from someone, especially a college or university student who doesn't want to engage in or cooperate in academic growth or research activities.
- 2- The second limitation involved was the pandemic (Covid-19) which was the reason we didn't collect some of the data properly
- 3- Some students were perplexed by some statements on the scales during data collection, which may have led them to answer wrongly or improperly.

Suggestions for future work

Future research work should be done individually by focusing on other variables at a time and investigating their relationships and interdependencies in greater detail. Those scales should be used which have less items so students will fill the questionnaires properly. Future study should be conducted on a big sample and should be more widely distributed and drawn from Pakistan's numerous colleges and universities. Professionals such as doctors, engineers, scientists, and teachers could be studied in the future.

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